

Research Article**Comparison of Recurrence Rate of Pterygium between the Patients Managed
With Auto Graft and Bare-Sclera****¹Muhammad Younis Tahir, ²Mahwish Saeed
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Quaid-e-Azam Medical College/BVH, Bahawalpur²House Officer, Bahawal Victoria Hospital, Bahawalpur³Bahawal Victoria Hospital, Bahawalpur**ABSTRACT**

Introduction: Pterygium appears as a fleshy vascular mass that occurs in the inter palpebral fissure. The typical pterygium is triangular in shape and is made up of a cap, head and body. It is more frequently located nasally rather than temporally. The cause of pterygium is not known but those who work outside in the sun and wind are more prone to develop pterygium probably from conjunctival irritation and is more common in tropical & subtropical region with a reported prevalence of 2 to 7 % worldwide.

Objectives: To compare the frequency of recurrence of pterygium between the patients managed with auto graft and Bare-sclera

Study design: Randomized Controlled Trial.

Settings: The study was conducted at Department of Ophthalmology, Bahawal Victoria Hospital, Bahawalpur.

Duration of study: From March 2017 to September 2017 over the period of 6 months

Results: Total 92 patients were selected for this study. Mean age of the patients was 40.12 ± 13.843 years, mean age of group A was 39.63 ± 13.468 years and mean age of group B was 40.61 ± 14.339 years.

Out of 46 patients of group A, recurrence of pterygium was noted in 7 (15.22%) patients. In group B, recurrence of pterygium was noted in 17 (36.96%) patients. Significantly higher difference of recurrence of pterygium between the both groups was noted with p value 0.0314.

Conclusion: In this study higher rate of recurrence of pterygium was noted in Bare-sclera group as compared to auto graft group.

Key words: Pterygium recurrence, bare sclera

INTRODUCTION

Pterygium appears as a fleshy vascular mass that occurs in the inter palpebral fissure. The typical pterygium is triangular in shape and is made up of a cap, head and body. It is more frequently located nasally rather than temporally.¹ The cause of pterygium is not known but those who work

outside in the sun and wind are more prone to develop pterygium probably from conjunctival irritation and is more common in tropical & subtropical region with a reported prevalence of 2 to 7 % worldwide.^{2,3} It is more frequent in areas with more ultraviolet radiation, especially UVR-A

and UVR-B (290-400nm) is considered the most dangerous.⁴

The mainstay of treatment is surgical. Various surgical procedures are used to treat pterygium. Total excision of the lesion was practiced in the ancient times, which still constitutes one of the methods of treatment. The excision of a pterygium with bare sclera was widely practiced because it was believed to be safe and simple. However, with time it becomes apparent that the recurrence rate was unacceptably high ranging from 24% to 89%.⁵ The recurrence rate is significant and recurrent pterygia are often worse than primary ones.⁶ A recurrent pterygium can be associated with decreased visual acuity due to involvement of visual axis and/or irregular astigmatism, extra ocular motility restriction and symblepharon (scarring and adhesions between palpebral and bulbar conjunctiva) formation.⁶

Kenyon et al, first described a conjunctival auto graft in 1985. They reported a recurrence rate of 5.3% and infrequent and relatively minor complications. The primary disadvantage of this procedure is the prolonged operative time as compared to the bare sclera technique.⁷

Pterygium is preventable cause of visual loss in Southern Punjab. Its prevalence is very high.

Surgical treatment remains the treatment of choice once the pterygium is found to be progressive in nature. A number of surgical techniques have been described as methods for pterygium treatment including bare sclera resection and pterygium excision plus conjunctival autograft placement. The main difference between bare sclera resection and conjunctival autograft placement is that a free conjunctival graft usually from the superior bulbar conjunctiva is sutured over the denuded sclera following the pterygium resection.

The climate of Southern Punjab is a hot and sandy, people are more exposed to ultraviolet rays and the ultraviolet rays is a factor to develop pterygium. Results of this study may guide that which procedure has minimum pterygium reoccurrence rate in patients who managed with auto graft or Bare-sclera for the treatment of pterygium.

OPERATIONAL DEFINITION

Pterygium:

A fleshy mass of thickened conjunctiva that grows over part of the cornea usually from the inner side of the eyeball.

Recurrence of pterygium:

A fleshy mass of thickened conjunctiva that grows again after 6 months follow up.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This comparative study was conducted at Department of Ophthalmology, Bahawal Victoria Hospital, Bahawalpur from March 2017 to September 2017 over the period of 6 months.

Inclusion Criteria:

- All the patients with pterygium encroaching over the cornea ≥ 2 mm from ≥ 1 year.
- Age from 20 to 60 years.
- Both male and female.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients with ocular surface abnormalities. (conjunctivitis and corneal ulcer on slit lamp examination)
- Patients with lid abnormalities. (entropion and ectropion on slit lamp examination)
- Patients with ocular or adnexal infections. (dacryocystitis on slit lamp examination)
- Known diabetic and hypertensive patients. (on history)

Data collection procedure:

Total 92 patients were included in this study after scrutinized by inclusion criteria and after taking written consent from Institutional Review Board. Written consent was taken from every patient. All included patients for surgery (auto graft or Bare-sclera) was offered to pick up a slip from total mixed up slips (half-slips was contain letter "A" and other half-slips contain letter "B") and he/she was placed in that group (Group-A or Group-B according to slip). Group-A was include those patients who were undergo auto graft technique and Group-B was include those patients who were undergo Bare-sclera.

Clinical examination of the patients including visual acuity, still lamp examination was performed. Post-operative Recurrence of pterygium was assessed after 3 months follow-up.

Demographic data including age, gender, type of surgery was entered into a predesigned proforma.

Data analysis procedure:

The data was entered in SPSS V16 for statistical analysis. Quantitative variable like age and duration of pterygium was presented as mean ± SD, while qualitative variable like gender and frequency of recurrence of pterygium was presented in frequency and percentages. Chi-square test was applied to compare the frequency of recurrence of pterygium in both groups. Stratification was done for age, gender and duration of pterygium. Post stratification. Chi-square test was applied to see effect of these on outcome variable i.e. recurrence of pterygium. P-values ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

Total 92 patients were selected for this study. Mean age of the patients was 40.12 ± 13.843 years, mean age of group A was 39.63 ± 13.468 years and mean age of group B was 40.61 ± 14.339 years. Out of 46 patients of group A, recurrence of pterygium was noted in 7 (15.22%) patients. In group B, recurrence of pterygium was noted in 17 (36.96%) patients. Significantly higher difference of recurrence of pterygium

between the both groups was noted with p value 0.0314. (Table 1)

Selected patients were divided into two age groups i.e. age group 20-40 years and age group 41-60 years. Total 23 patients of group A and 22 patients of group B belonged to age group 20-40 years. Recurrence of pterygium was noted in 3 (13.04%) patients and 9 (40.91%) patients of group A and B and the difference was statistically significant with p value 0.0472. Total 23 patients of group A and 24 patients of group B belonged to age group 41-60 years. Recurrence of pterygium was noted in 4 (17.39%) patients of group A and 8 (33.33%) patients of group B. But the difference was statistically insignificant with p value 0.3177. (Table 2)

Male patients were 27 and 28 respectively in group A and B. Recurrence rate was 4 (14.81%) and 11 (39.29%) male patients of group A and B. Difference of recurrence between both group was statistically insignificant with p value 0.0683. There were 19 female patients in group A and recurrence rate was 3 (15.79%), while 18 female patients were in group B and recurrence rate was 6 (33.33%). Difference of recurrence rate was statistically insignificant with p value 0.2691. (Table 3)

Table 1: Comparison of Recurrence between both groups

Group	Recurrence		Total	P value
	Yes	No		
A	7 (15.22%)	39 (84.78%)	46	0.0314
B	17 (36.96%)	29 (63.04%)	46	

Table 2: Comparison of Recurrence between both groups for age groups

Group	Recurrence		Total	P value
	Yes	No		
age group 20-40 years				
A	3 (13.04%)	20 (86.969%)	23	0.0472
B	9 (40.91%)	13 (59.09%)	22	
age group 41-60 years				
A	4 (17.39%)	19 (82.61%)	23	0.3177
B	8 (33.33%)	16 (66.67%)	24	

Table 3: Comparison of Recurrence between both groups for gender

Group	Recurrence		Total	P value
	Yes	No		
Male patients				
A	4 (14.81%)	23 (85.19%)	27	0.0683
B	11 (39.29%)	17 (60.71%)	28	
Female patients				
A	3 (15.79%)	16 (84.21%)	19	0.2691
B	6 (33.33%)	12 (66.67%)	18	

DISCUSSION

The pterygium is one of the commonest disorders in a tropical country such as Pakistan.⁸ Exposure to ultra violet light is presumed to be the most important risk factor. A wide range of surgical procedures for removal of pterygium have been used.⁹ However, recurrence after pterygium excision without any adjunctive therapy has been reported to be as high as 30% to 88% especially in hot dry and sunny atmosphere. A recurrent pterygium can be associated with decreased visual acuity due to involvement of visual axis and/or irregular astigmatism, extraocular motility restriction and symblepharon formation.⁹

Mean age of the patients was 40.12 ± 13.843 years, mean age of group A was 39.63 ± 13.468 years and mean age of group B was 40.61 ± 14.339 years. In one study by Narsaniet al⁶ mean age of the patients was 43.26 ± 12.81 years which is comparable with our study. Ahmed et al¹⁰ reported mean age of the patients as 40 years which is also comparable with our findings.

Out of 46 patients of group A (auto graft), recurrence of pterygium was noted in 7 (15.22%) patients. In group B (Bare-sclera), recurrence of pterygium was noted in 17 (36.96%) patients. Significantly (P = 0.0314) higher pterygium recurrence rate was noted in Bare-sclera group as compared to auto graft group.

In one study by Ahmed et al¹⁰ recurrence of pterygium was noted in (10%) with conjunctival autograft and (60%) in bare sclera technique. Findings of this study are in agreement with our

study. In another study by Rafiq et al,¹¹ in bare sclera group, recurrence of pterygium rate was 70% while in conjunctival autograft group, it was 08% which are also in favour of our study.

In another study by Khan et al,⁵ in bare sclera group, recurrence of pterygium rate was 36.6% while in conjunctival autograft group, it was 8.8%. Akhter et al¹² reported recurrence of pterygium in 7.96% patients managed with auto graft method. In this study 57.69% patients were male and 42.31% patients were female. Recurrence of pterygium was noted in 2 (7.96%) male patients and in 2 (100%) female patients. In our study Recurrence rate of pterygium was 4 (14.81%) in male patients and 3(15.79%) in female patients who were managed with auto graft. Kim observed statistically similar recurrence rates, 8.0% for auto-graft group versus 8.6% for rotational flap group.¹³

Total 23 patients of group A and 22 patients of group B belonged to age group 20-40 years. Recurrence of pterygium was noted in 3 (13.04%) patients and 9 (40.91%) patients of group A and B and the difference was statistically significant with p value 0.0472.

Total 23 patients of group A and 24 patients of group B belonged to age group 41-60 years. Recurrence of pterygium was noted in 4 (17.39%) patients of group A and 8 (33.33%) patients of group B. But the difference was statistically insignificant with p value 0.3177.

In one study by Latha et al¹⁴ highest numbers of patients were in the age group 40-49 years(32 %). Lowest numbers of cases were in the age

group ≥ 60 (14 %). Essumanet al¹⁵ reported overall recurrence of pterygium in 22(37%) patients managed with auto graft. Chan et al¹⁶ found recurrence of pterygium in 6.3% patients managed with auto graft technique.

Our study suggested a relationship between age and recurrence of pterygium. Youth is associated with increasing risk of recurrence and as the age advances, chances of recurrences become less and less.

CONCLUSION

In this study higher rate of recurrence of pterygium was noted in Bare-sclera group as compared to auto graft group. In younger age group, patients of Bare-sclera group found with higher rate of recurrence as compared to auto graft group.

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